

Developing teachers' professional performance based on dual intelligence: a mediation perspective

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ABSTRACT

Teacher professional performance is crucial for schools to improve students' academic performance and success. However, research on this issue still needs to be completed, including the factors influencing it. Therefore, this study focuses on investigating the role of interpersonal communication skills (ICS) in mediating cultural intelligence (CI) and emotional intelligence (EI) affect teachers' professional performance. The participants are 455 Indonesian teachers selected by accidental sampling from three provinces in Indonesia. Data was collected by distributing Likert scale questionnaires and analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM) performed by LisRel 8.80. All hypotheses were supported (significant). It means CI, EI, and ICS are related to teachers' professional performance; CI and EI link to teachers' ICS; and ICS mediates CI and EI affect teachers' professional performance. This evidence promotes a new model of CI and EI affecting teachers' professional performance via ICS. It provides a theoretical contribution, and practical implication requires critical discussion among researchers, scientists, and practitioners.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The professional performance of teachers is the basis for schools to respond to real problems and challenges. It happened because, empirically, teachers' professional competence has been proven to be reliable in increasing student academic achievement [1]. Teachers' professionalism also determines student success [2]. Additionally, other studies reveal that teachers' professional development contributes to students' achievement [3] and academic performance [4]. It shows that a teacher's professional performance is an essential determinant of student academic achievement. Therefore, low student academic achievement can signal the "dark side" of teachers' professional performance. In cases when the results of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) evaluation in 2018 on the reading ability of Indonesian students were low, ranking 72 out of 77 countries, and the results of the national computer-based assessment in Indonesian indicated that 50% of pupils failed to meet the basic literacy competency and 67% failed to meet the numeracy literacy competency (2021). This, among other things, indicates that teachers' professional performance deserves to be questioned and investigated.

Several studies indicate that cultural intelligence (CI), emotional intelligence (EI), and interpersonal communication skills (ICS) can influence professional performance. For example, the researchers proved that CI has a significant relationship with professional competency and performance [5]–[7]. Several other

investigations claimed that EI influences professional competence and performance [8], [9]. Further, a recent study indicated that ICS impacts performance [10]. However, other studies also revealed that ICS can be affected by CI [11] and EI [12], [13]. Nevertheless, contradictory results were discovered in another research. For instance, EI has no significant effect on performance [14], ICS does not affect performance [15], [16], and EI does not support interpersonal communication [17]. In addition, CI is also not a good predictor of performance [18]. The inconsistency of the results of this study requires scientific clarification so as not to cause confusion among academics and practitioners. Therefore, this study aims to explore the professional performance of teachers based on dual intelligence (CI and EI) mediated by the ICS perspective.

In this paper, the term teacher professional performance is defined as a series of behaviors related to their duties or work at school, which are designed and dedicated to achieving task/work requirements to realize the school organization's goals. This concept is built on professionals and performance. In education, professional teachers carry out their professional duties with total dedication and responsibility according to applicable standards by utilizing their knowledge and skills [19]. Meanwhile, performance is about actions, behavior, or what employees do [20]. It is a series of work behaviors designed and dedicated to achieving organizational goals [21]. In line with these two notions, Mawarto *et al.* [22] stated that professional performance is works related behavior designed and dedicated to achieving job requirements and realizing organizational goals. Makovec [23] mentions several measurement indicators of teacher professionalism. The first is subjects, which are mastering, reviewing, evaluating, and updating knowledge related to the detail of the subject matter being taught. Second, didactic–transmitting knowledge to students using various methods and considering class conditions and personal characteristics. Third, pedagogic–direction and interest in the problems faced by students, solving educational issues inside and outside the classroom, and acting respectfully, ethically, decisively, and consistently.

Professional performance can be influenced by CI, EI, and ICS. About CI, nowadays, it is getting incredible attention from researchers. The triggers are CI has been shown to influence the behavior, performance, and success of individuals, teams, and organizations, life satisfaction, and can even change cultural conditions. For example, CI significantly influences work-related outcomes [24], knowledge sharing and process [25], [26], and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) [11]. CI also impacts performance at an individual [7], [27] and organizational level [28], and influences team effectiveness [29]. Other studies demonstrated that CI impacts service quality [30] and adaptive selling behaviors [31]. The recent investigation also proves that CI is linked with burnout [32]. Moreover, CI is quite effective increasing life satisfaction [33], [34]. Therefore, CI is an individual capital that is increasingly valuable and valuable for employees, managers, organizations, and employers [35].

The cultural intelligence concept was built to answer actual needs in thinking, behaving, and acting appropriately and carefully in diverse cultures; it requires more specific intelligence and is not enough to use general intelligence [36]. It indicates a paradigm shift from initially focusing on cross-cultural comparisons to intercultural skills [37]. CI is a person's capacity to interact and adapt with other people from various cultural backgrounds. It reflects capacity to interact intensely and effectively with others from different cultural backgrounds [27]. CI also refers to a person's ability to adapt to other people in different cultural settings, especially when there are conflicts or problems [38]. It reflects the individual's capability to adapt to the uniqueness of various cultures [39]. CI comprises three indicators. The first is knowledge, which refers to personal understanding and mastery of culture, cultural diversity, and how culture affects one's skills and behavior. Second, mindfulness–personal intention to be open-minded and utilize the situation to support understanding. Third, behavioral skills–the capability to perform social behavior skills in a new cultural setting [40].

Teachers with good knowledge, mindfulness, and behavioral skills about culture have an easier time understanding and adapting to students from various cultural backgrounds. This can then make it easier for them to transfer knowledge and help solve problems faced by students. Thus, CI has a positive correlation with professional performance. However, so far, research explicitly investigating the relationship between CI and professional performance is still a challenge. Nevertheless, quite many studies point to the effect of CI on professionalism and performance. For example, CI affects teachers' professional capacities [41], professional competency [5], and management competencies [6]. In addition, scholars also reveal that CI has a significant effect on performance [6], [7], [42], [43], including task performance [44], [45], leadership performance [46], proactive service performance [47], and organizational performance [28]. Hence, this issue is exciting and urgent to be investigated. Accordingly, we promote the first hypothesis: CI has a relationship with teachers' professional performance (H1).

Such cultural intelligence, emotional intelligence also consistently receives serious attention from researchers in the last three decades. For instance, prior studies have discovered an association between EI and professional, organizational, and project commitment [48]–[50]. EI also impacts quality of work-life [51], job satisfaction [52], career adaptability [53], and performance [54], [55]. In addition, EI also influence anxiety [56]. In educational context, EI are related to language achievement, learners' academic literacy

development, and attitudes toward digital competence [57]–[59]. Hence, EI is vital in all phases of life, from young to old age. In the elderly, EI can help reduce isolation and loneliness to improve quality of life and contribute to mental and physical health. It suggests that EI affects various aspects of individual and organizational life [60]. EI is an individual's ability to recognize, understand, and control emotions when interacting socially with other people. It reflects a person's capability to recognize, understand, and control his own emotions and those of others in interacting socially effectively [61], [62]. Therefore, EI is a broad-dimensional competency that involves the cognitive processing of emotions and information related to emotions [53].

Individuals with high emotional intelligence can understand, regulate, and control their and others' emotions better [63] and understand the motives that trigger their behavior of themselves and others [64]. EI consists of five indicators. First, self-awareness refers to being aware of other people's feelings and using them as preferences in making judgments, building trust, and making decisions. Second, self-regulation is the capacity to manage emotions effectively, including delaying gratification and increasing the tolerance threshold for stress. Third, motivation relates to the use of preferences as a guide and motivator in taking initiatives, mobilizing efforts, and achieving goals and staying motivated even in a downturn. Fourth, empathy is the ability to feel what other people feel. Fifth, relationship management is related to expressing emotions in social interactions by considering the social situations context and utilizing interpersonal skills to establish partnerships with others [65].

Teachers with high emotional intelligence will likely have good professional performance, reflected in their mastery of learning materials, transferring knowledge, and solving various student problems. Although specific studies on the relationship between EI and professional performance remain to be found, several previous studies indicated a significant effect of EI on professional competence and performance. For example, prove that EI impacts professional competence [9], [66]. Other studies also indicate that EI affects performance [8], [67]–[69], including contextual performance [70], task performance [71], and firm performance [72]. Therefore, we formulate the second hypothesis: EI has a relationship with teachers' professional performance (H2).

Interpersonal communication skills is now increasingly popular as empirical evidence is found about its influence on various aspects of the lives of individuals, groups, and organizations. ICS is a person's capability to exchange information between two or more people verbally or nonverbally to achieve goals. Empirically, ICS are crucial for maintaining interpersonal relationships and effective functioning in a work setting [73]. ICS also fluency communication between individuals [74] and effective to increase information service delivery [75]. Hence, interpersonal communication influences OCB [76] and professional growth [77]. In educational context, ICS has significantly impacted student's learning outcomes [78], and reduces student's loneliness [79]. Moreover, ICS also increases organizational effectiveness [80]. Traditionally, interpersonal communication is an information exchange between two or more people interdependently in verbal and nonverbal interaction to accomplish personal and relational goals [77], [81], [82]. It can occur face-to-face between individuals or in certain social settings, for example, groups or organizations [83], either offline or online. Interpersonal communication comprises five indicators.

First, openness relates to the willingness to express oneself and act when interacting socially with others honestly. Second, empathy reflects the tendency to feel what others feel without ignoring their own identity. Third, a supportive attitude is being tolerant and open-minded and respecting other people's and opponents' viewpoints. The fourth is positiveness, being positive, and appreciating interaction partners. Fifth, equality relates to the view that differences are acceptable conditions for solving problems or disputes [82]. For teachers, ICS is needed to develop social relations between school members, especially with students. Teachers with high openness, empathy, supportive and positive attitudes, will tend to find it easier to establish social relations with students, making it easier for them to carry out the learning process effectively. Several prior studies also indicated that ICS is related to professional performance. For example, ICS influences professional growth [77]. Other studies indicated that it significantly affects performance [10], [84], [85]. Hence, we propose the third hypothesis: ICS has a relationship with teachers' professional performance (H3)

Interpersonal communication skills has a unique position. Besides influencing teachers' professional performance, it is also affected by CI. Scholars claim that CI has a significant relationship with ICS. For example, CI has a significant relationship with interpersonal communication [8], [86], [87], a good predictor of communication skills [88] and interpersonal process effectiveness [89]. It addressed that CI is crucial antecedence of ICS. As an illustration, teachers with excellent knowledge, mindfulness, and behavioral skills about culture will tend to find it easier to establish interpersonal communication with students who have diverse cultural backgrounds. It conditions will make teachers more open, empathetic, positive, and supportive in establishing interactions with students to create a conducive and harmonious reciprocal relationship. Thus, we can promote the fourth hypothesis: CI has a relationship with teachers' ICS (H4).

Interpersonal communication skills is also influenced by EI. Previous studies have conclusively proven that EI has a significant relationship with interpersonal communication [12], [13], [90]. Other studies also revealed that EI is linked with communication skills [62], [91]. In addition, EI can determine communication ethics [92]. It suggests that EI is an essential predictor for ICS. As an illustration, teachers with high EI will find it easier to communicate interpersonally with students. For example, teachers with good self-awareness, self-regulation, and relationship management will likely have a positive and supportive attitude that students need in the learning process, especially students who have difficulty mastering subject matter. Therefore, we formulate the fifth hypothesis: EI has a relationship with teachers' ICS (H5).

So far, research specifically identifying ICS's mediates role in the causal relationship between CI and EI with professional performance is still a challenge. However, several research results position ICS as a mediator between CI and EI with professional performance. For example, several studies proved that CI is significantly related to interpersonal communication [11] and EI affects communication skills [12], [13]; meanwhile, other study found that ICS impacts performance [10]. These studies' results indicate that ICS has the opportunity to mediate the relationship between CI and EI with professional performance. Therefore, this study explores it to find a mediating model of ICS's role in the relationship between CI and EI with professional performance. Based on these, we propose two hypotheses of mediation as: CI has a relationship with teachers' professional performance through ICS (H6) and EI has a relationship with teachers' professional performance through ICS (H7).

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design and measurement

A quantitative approach with a survey shared online by email and WhatsApp application were used in this study. The survey uses a questionnaire on a Likert scale with five options, from strongly disagree/never (score=1) to strongly agree/always (score=5). Researchers constructed a questionnaire that referred to experts' theoretical dimensions or indicators. CI indicators consist of knowledge (Know), mindfulness (Mind), and behavioral skills (BS) [40]. EI indicators include self-awareness (SA), self-regulation (SR), motivation (Mot), empathy (Emp), and relationship management (RM) [65]. The ICS indicators consist of openness (Open), empathy (Emp), supportiveness (Sup), positiveness (Pos), and equality (Equ) [82]. Finally, subjects (Sub), didactic (Did), and pedagogic (Ped) are professional performance indicators [23]. As presented in Table 1, CI, EI, ICS, and professional performance comprise six, ten, eight, and nine items each. Corrected item-total correlation coefficient and alpha coefficient of all constructs more than 0.361 and 0.70. It indicates a valid and reliable instrument [93]. Therefore, a questionnaire can be used to collect the research data. Before being analyzed, the data obtained was tested with a statistical approach of correlational and Harman's single-factor test to anticipate the possibility of common method bias (CMB) accrued. The results show the correlation coefficient between constructs/variables is smaller than 0.90, while the total variance extracted by one factor is 33.852, smaller than 50%. Therefore, it indicated no CMB in this study's data [94], [95].

2.2. Participants

The research participants as the samples are 455 junior and senior high school teachers determined by accidental sampling from three provinces in Indonesia, namely Jakarta Capital Special Region, West Java, and Banten. The number of samples is suitable with the threshold number of samples required in structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis, namely 10 times the number of indicators, which in this study is 16 indicators [93]. Most of them are female (71.43%), married (81.54%), and have a bachelor's education (92.09%). There are 61.09% teachers in junior high school and 38.9% in senior high school. Their work experience as a teacher was >16 years (28.35%), <5 years (26.59%), 6-10 years (22.64%), and 11-15 years (22.42%). Finally, their age was 26-35 years (36.92%), 36-45 years (28.13%), 46-55 years (21.1%), <25 years (7.03%), and >56 years (6.81%).

2.3. Data analysis

Data analysis began with validity and reliability analysis at the instrument testing stage, followed by CMB, descriptive, and correlational analysis. All of it proceeded by SPSS version 22. Finally, as the primary analysis, hypothesis testing was carried out with SEM analysis supplemented by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and model fit test (GOF) performed using LisRel 8.80.

Table 1. Research instrument

Variables	Indicators	Items	
CI	Know	I understand the meaning of culture and its diversity. I understand how culture affects behavior.	
	Mind	I respect the opinions of other people from different cultural backgrounds. I learn from the lives of other people from different cultural backgrounds.	
	BS	I easily interact socially with people from different cultural backgrounds. I quickly adjust to a new culture.	
EI	SA	I really understand my capabilities as a teacher. I believe I can solve various problems that arise at school.	
	SR	I use the power of emotions to fight for life goals that have not been achieved. I know the right way to express my feelings.	
	Mot	I actively take the initiative to help students solve problems. I am enthusiastic about facing various challenges.	
	Emp	I can feel what other people feel. I easily build social relationships with diverse people.	
	RM	I consider social situations when interacting with other people. I prioritize a persuasive approach in resolving disputes.	
	ICS	Open	I provide information honestly (according to the facts) to others. I welcome input from other people.
		Emp	I am enthusiastic about listening to other people when they talk. I trust other people when they share experiences.
Sup		I respect the uniqueness of the interlocutor. I show support for the other person's opposing views.	
Pos		I sincerely appreciate the aspirations of others.	
Professional performance	Equ	I view differences as a gift of life that deserves to be cherished.	
	Sub	I master the subject matter that I teach. I evaluate the subject matter routinely. I update the subject matter regularly.	
	Did	I use various teaching methods varied. I consider the characteristics of students in delivering the subject matter. I take into account class dynamics in teaching.	
	Ped		I pay attention to students' learning interest in teaching. I take into account the actual condition of the student's personality in the learning process.
			I focus on solving various learning problems faced by students.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Descriptive and correlation analysis

Generally, the mean value, ranging from 4.18 to 12.64, is greater than the standard deviation value, typically between 0.747 and 1.997. It reflects a suitable data representation and deserves further analysis. Meanwhile, correlation analysis showed that all indicators had a significant relationship with the others at $p < 0.01$, with a correlation coefficient range of 0.12 to 0.57. It indicates that all indicators have a mutually beneficial reciprocal relationship with each other. However, these relationships did not indicate multicollinearity symptoms because the correlation coefficient was more than 0.8.

3.2. Measurement model estimate

The measurement model estimates by CFA, as summarized in Table 2, indicated that factors' loading values of all indicators > 0.3 . It indicates validity indicators in conducting measurement functions to constructs/variables [96]. Meanwhile, the reliability of the construct/variables can be determined based on the construct reliability (CR), average variance extracted (AVE), and Cronbach's alpha (CA) values. Generally, all variables' CR and CA values are more than 0.70, and the VE is greater than 0.50, indicating good reliability and an acceptable convergence for all variables [93]. It means that all indicators can measure or represent constructs/variables.

3.3. Goodness fit index (GOF)

The GOF statistical analysis results showed that nine of eleven criteria were a good fit, namely: goodness fit index, root mean square of approximation, normed fit index, non-normed fit index, adjusted goodness fit index, comparative fit index, relative fit index, parsimony normed of fit index, and normed chi-square. Meanwhile, the second criteria that were not fulfilled (poor fit) are chi-square and significant probability. In this case, the Chi-square test is susceptible to a large sample size, more than 200 [93]; such as this study involving 455 teachers; as a result, the Chi-square test was poor. even so, the GOF results are still valid (fit) because most indices obtained (9 out of 11) are suitable for the criteria. It means the theoretical model built on relevant previous research is suitable with the empirical model constructed based on research data. Under this condition, the new empirical model produced by this study is credible.

Table 2. Results of the measurement model

Constructs	Indicators	Factor loading	CR	AVE	CA
CI	Know	.50	.724	.565	.868
	Mind	.75			
	BS	.53			
EI	SA	.38	.707	.512	.853
	SR	.53			
	Mot	.66			
	Emp	.62			
	RM	.56			
ICS	Open	.64	.817	.572	.829
	Emp	.74			
	Sup	.71			
	Pos	.69			
	Equ	.65			
Professional performance	Sub	.66	.742	.579	.898
	Did	.87			
	Ped	.55			

3.4. Hypothesis testing

All hypotheses of this study are significant (supported) at $\alpha < 0.05$ and 0.01 . As visualized in Figure 1, Figure 2, and summarized in Table 3, CI, EI, and ICS significantly related to teachers' professional performance, with path coefficient (γ/β) and p value, respectively: $\gamma=0.26, p<0.05$; $\gamma=0.28, p<0.05$; and $\beta=0.28, p<0.01$. It addresses that CI, EI, and ICS are vital predictors for teachers' professional performance, so their existence is worth considering when trying to improve teachers' professional performance. In addition, CI and EI are significantly linked to teachers' ICS, with path coefficient and p value: $\gamma=0.32, p<0.05$, and $\gamma=0.34, <0.05$.

It shows that CI and EI are essential antecedents for teachers' ICS; therefore, both need to be considered in improving the teacher's ICS. Lastly, ICS significant mediates the relationship between CI and EI with teachers' professional performance ($\beta=0.09, p<0.01$). It indicates the vital role of ICS in mediating the relationship between CI and EI and teacher' professional performance. All path coefficient results were positive. It indicates that an improvement in one variable (independent/exogenous) will be followed by an increase in another variable (dependent/endogenous). For example, improving CI can enhance teachers' professional performance.

Figure 1. Standardized structural model

Figure 2. T-value structural model

Table 3. Hypothesis-testing results

Hypothesis	γ/β	T-value	Decision
H ₁ : CI and teachers' professional performance	.26*	1.72	Supported
H ₂ : EI and teachers' professional performance	.28*	1.90	Supported
H ₃ : ICS and teachers' professional performance	.28**	3.84	Supported
H ₄ : CI and teachers' ICS	.32*	2.09	Supported
H ₅ : EI and teachers' ICS	.34*	2.25	Supported
H ₆ : CI and teachers' professional performance through ICS	.09**	7.81	Supported
H ₇ : EI and teachers' professional performance through ICS	.09**	7.80	Supported

*p<0.05, **p<0.01

3.5. Discussion

This study found a significant relationship between CI, EI, and ICS with teachers' professional performance; CI and EI with teachers' ICS; and CI and EI with teachers' professional performance via ICS. Specifically, CI has a positive and significant relationship with teachers' professional performance. It indicates the vital role of CI for teachers' professional performance so that if teachers' CI is improved, it can increase teachers' professional performance. This finding is consistent with prior studies proved that CI influences teachers' professional capacities, competency, working, and performance [5]–[7], [41], [43], [97], and negates contradictory research results [18]. Thus, these findings confirm that CI is one of the critical factors determining teachers' professional performance, so its existence needs more attention from the school's stakeholders.

This study also declared a significant relationship between EI and teacher professional performance. This empirical evidence shows the exclusive role of EI as a predictor of teacher professional performance, where if a teacher's EI is sown well, there is a great chance of increasing teacher professional performance. This finding links similar studies that revealed that EI significantly relates to professional competence and performance [8], [9], [70]–[72], as well as eliminating the conflicting results of other studies [17]. It means that EI is a key factor that plays a critical role in improving teacher professional performance, so it should be prioritized. ICS was also shown to be positively and significantly related to teacher' professional performance in this study. This empirical fact confirms that ICS is a crucial antecedent for teachers' professional performance, which has the consequence that improving teacher ICS can enhance teachers' professional performance. Furthermore, this scientific evidence is in line with scholars' claim that ICS affects professional growth and performance [10], [77], [84], [85] and is the antithesis of contradictory research results [15], [16]. Thus, there is no need to doubt that the ICS plays a vital role in determining teachers' professional performance.

In addition, this study also found that CI and EI had a significant relationship with teachers' ICS. This confirms that CI and EI are predisposed to teacher ICS, which means that if both are well developed, it can have implications for improving teacher ICS. This finding confirms the results of previous studies, which

prove that CI has an effect on ICS [11], [86], [87] and EI has a positive effect on ICS [12], [13], [62]. In addition, it also negates the study that EI did not impact interpersonal communication [17]. It means that CI and EI are worth considering developing teachers' ICS.

Finally, this study proves the mediating effect of ICS in the links between CI and EI with teachers' professional performance. It shows the new empirical evidence concerning the mediating model of CI and EI relationship with teachers' professional performance through ICS. This finding confirms that ICS can effectively mediate CI and EI relationships with teachers' professional performance. It also means that when CI and EI are adequately developed, it can trigger improvements in teachers' ICS and then have implications for improving their professional performance. This finding promotes a new model between CI and EI with teachers' professional performance through ICS. The new model provides a crucial theoretical contribution to enriching studies on teachers' professional performance which are still limited, especially in relation to CI, EI, and ICS. The mediating role of ICS provides valuable new evidence for developing CI and EI for professional performance models with ICS mediation mechanisms. Furthermore, these findings are more broadly useful for several science disciplines, such as educational management, human resource management (HRM), and organizational behavior, and educational and organizational psychology. Therefore, researchers, academics, and scientists can utilize the new model in their future research projects in their respective fields of study. In addition, the findings of this study also provide practical implications for school management, especially improving teacher professional performance through CI and EI with ICS mediation mechanisms. Therefore, school principals can immediately and without hesitation try to direct teachers to increase teacher capacities of CI, EI, and ICS through various ways, such as collectively through training/workshops activities facilitated by schools or encouraging teachers to increase their capacity independently.

4. CONCLUSION

Teachers' professional performance is essential for schools to enhance student academic performance and success. Because of this, it is essential and urgent to investigate teacher professional performance from the CI, EI, and ICS perspectives. This study found a significant relationship between CI, EI, and ICS with teachers' professional performance, CI and EI with teachers' ICS, and CI and EI with teachers' professional performance through ICS. This finding clarifies not only several previous studies' results that were used as a reference for the development of this research hypothesis and counteracted the contradictory results of other studies but also shows new findings of the mediating role of ICS in the causal relationship between CI and EI and teachers' professional performance. Therefore, this study promotes a new relationship model between CI and EI with teachers' professional performance through ICS. It provides a crucial theoretical contribution to enriching studies on teachers' professional performance, especially concerning CI, EI, and ICS, which are useful for several relevant sciences. In addition, it also provides practical implications for school management to improve teachers' professional performance via CI and EI with the ICS mediation mechanism. Thus, the new model deserves critical discussion by researchers, academics, and practitioners before being adapted or adopted for their future work.

Although this study was performed thoughtfully and carefully through strict scientific procedures, some limitations are difficult to avoid and require improvement in the future. For example, this research only accommodates theoretical dimensions/indicators from several experts, even though several dimensions/indicators from other experts can be considered. In addition, this research only uses a quantitative approach, even though a qualitative approach can be involved to enrich and deepen the research results. This research also only focuses on one data source (teachers), even though other data sources can be utilized, such as school principals, administrative staff, and students. Finally, this research sample only comes from specific geographic locations with cultures, even though it can be expanded to other locations and cultures. Therefore, future research of this kind needs to consider different dimensions/indicators, use mixed methods (quantitative and qualitative), use more complete research data sources, and add some samples from other geographic locations and cultures.

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